

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Molecular Detection of Drug-Resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Sputum Specimens from the New and Previously Treated Tuberculosis Cases at the National Reference Chest Diseases Laboratory in Lusaka, Zambia

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ABSTRACT

Background: Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis (DR-TB) is one of the major public health issues globally. Zambia is highly burdened by TB and multi-drug resistant TB. In this study, sputum samples obtained from the new and previously treated cases of TB were examined for drug-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB).

Methods: Sputum specimens were processed using the N-acetyl-L-cysteine-sodium hydroxide method, stained and examined using fluorescent technique and microscopy respectively. Mycobacterial DNA was extracted using the Genolyse kit, then subjected to multiplex polymerase chain reaction amplification and reverse hybridization. Drug-resistance and mutations in MTB genes were detected using the Genotype MTBDR_{plus} VER 2.0 and MTBDR_s/ VER 2.0 assays.

Results: A total of 329 MTB-positive sputum specimens, 102 from the new TB cases and 227 from previously treated TB cases, were analysed for drug-resistance. Among the new TB cases, 3.9% had Rifampicin (RIF) mono-resistance, 12.8% Isoniazid (INH) mono-resistance, and 17.7% had Multi-Drug Resistance (MDR). For the previously treated TB cases, 10.1% had RIF mono-resistance, 6.6% INH mono-resistance, 33.0% MDR, 1.8% poly-drug resistance, and 0.8% had pre-Extensively Drug-Resistance (pre-XDR). Mutations identified were *rpoB* (Ser531Leu, His526Asp, Asp516Val, His526Tyr, and Glu510His), *katG* (Ser315Thr 1 and Ser315Thr 2), *InhA* (Cys15Thr), *gyrA* (Ala90Val and Asp94Gly), and *eis* (Cys14Thr), each with a varying frequency.

Conclusion: DR-TB is prevalent, especially MDR-TB, which is currently the most worrisome form of DR-TB and an emerging threat hampering efforts in the control of TB in Zambia. The early detection and effective treatment of TB cases are key in the control of DR-TB.

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the leading causes of death globally [1,2]. This airborne killer infectious disease causes high mortality and morbidity rates [3-5]. The *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB) is the major causative agent for human TB

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among the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* Complex (MTBC), as it causes 97-99% of TB cases [6]. Globally 10 million individuals contract TB and from this number, 1.6 million individuals die from the disease [7]. The World Health Organization (WHO) global TB report of 2020 revealed that in 2019 there were 10 million people who got sick of TB, with 1,408,000 deaths globally [8].

Drug-resistant TB is a serious public health problem globally [9]. TB prevention, control, eradication and elimination strategies are being hampered by the successful transmission of drug-resistant MTB strains which are causing Multidrug-Resistant (MDR) and Extensively Drug-Resistant (XDR)-TB in the human population [10,11]. In 2020 the global prevalence of MDR/RR (Rifampicin-Resistance) was 3.3% among the new TB cases and 17.7% among the previously treated TB cases [8]. In 2019 was 3.4% and 18% among the new and previously treated TB cases respectively [12]. In 2017, 8.5% of TB patients diagnosed with MDR-TB progressed to developing XDR-TB [12]. XDR-TB is rapidly spreading throughout the world with 9.4 million new cases and 1.7 million reported deaths annually [13]. Globally in 2019 the prevalence of isoniazid mono-resistance among the new TB cases was 7.2% and 11.6% among the previously treated TB cases [8]. Drug-resistant TB is a serious public health threat in sub-Saharan Africa, especially for countries that have a high burden of both HIV and TB cases [14]. Drug-resistant TB is posing a huge obstacle for many countries to achieve the set WHO end TB targets [12,15].

Zambia is ranked among the top ten countries with a high burden of TB in the world [12,16,17]. TB is a major public health problem in the country, and is causing high mortality and morbidity rates [18-21]. Zambia is also among the top 10 countries in Africa with the highest cases of MDR/RR-TB [22]. MDR-TB is indeed a growing public health problem in the country [23]. In 2020, the MDR-TB prevalence rate in Zambia was 2.4% among the new and 18% previously treated TB cases [8]. While in 2019 was 2.8% and 18% among the new and previously treated TB cases respectively [12]. It has been projected that in 2021, Zambia will have a high burden of MDR and rifampicin-resistant TB cases [24].

Drug-resistant TB types include mono drug-resistant (resistance to any single anti-TB drug), poly drug-resistant (resistance to more than one anti-TB drug, other than both Rifampicin (RIF) and Isoniazid (INH) [25], MDR (resistance to at least INH and RIF), pre-XDR (resistance to INH, RIF, plus any one Fluoroquinolone (FLQ) (levofloxacin, ofloxacin, moxifloxacin or gatifloxacin) or any one of the Second-Line Injectable Drugs (SLIDs) (Kanamycin, Amikacin or Capreomycin), XDR (resistance to INH, RIF, plus any FLQ, plus any SLIDs) [26-30]. Poorly managed XDR-TB cases can progress to Totally Drug-Resistant TB (TDR-TB). TDR-TB is a type of DR-TB that is resistant to all first- and second-line anti-TB drugs. TDR-TB has been reported in India, Iran, Italy and South-Africa [31,32].

MTB develops resistance to anti-TB drugs due to a number of factors some of which include poor adherence, poor regimen selection, inadequate supply, and stock-out of anti-TB drugs [30,33]. However, research has shown that MTB resistance is mainly caused by mutations in the target genes and chromosomal replication errors [34,35].

Mutations in the *rpoB* gene, specifically in an 81 base pair region called the Rifampicin-Resistance Determining Region (RRDR) confer resistance to RIF [36,37]. The four most frequent mutations that confer resistance to RIF are Ser531Leu, His526Tyr, His526Asp, and Asp516Val [25]. Mutations in the *katG* and/or *inhA* gene cause resistance to INH frequently [36]. However, mutations in the following genes *ahpC*, *oxyR*, *kasA*, *furA*, *fabG* 1 and *ndh* infrequently cause resistance to INH [37]. The most frequent mutation in the *katG* gene that confers resistance to INH is the Ser315Thr mutation [37]. The four most frequent mutations in the *inhA* gene that confer resistance to INH are Cys15Thr, Ala16Gly, Thr8Cys and Thr8Ala [25]. Mutations occurring in the *katG* cause high-level resistance to INH, while those in the *inhA* cause low-level resistance [38].

Mutations occurring in the Quinolone Resistance Determining Region (QRDR) of both the *gyrA* and *gyrB* genes of resistant MTB strains cause resistance to the FLQs [39,40]. The most frequent mutations in the *gyrA* gene that confer resistance to the FLQs are Gly88Ala, Gly88Cys, Ala90Val, Ser91Pro, Asp94Ala, Asp94Asp, Asp94Tyr, Asp94Gly, and Asp94His. While those in the *gyrB* gene are Asp538Asp, Glu540Val [25]. It is worth noting that mutations in the *gyrA* gene confer a high-level resistance to FLQs, while those in the *gyrB* gene confer low-level resistance [41]. The frequency of mutations in the *gyrA* gene differ from one geographical location to another [41]. These differences are attributed to differences in treatment combinations containing FLQs used, and differences in geographic transmission environments for MTB [42]. Mutations in the *rrs*, *eis* and *tlyA* genes cause resistance to the aminoglycosides and cyclic polypeptide antibiotics [40]. The most frequent mutations in the *rrs* gene are Ala1401Gly, Cys1402Thr and Gly1484Thr [25,39]. While those in the *eis* gene are Gly37Thr, Cys14Thr, Cys12Thr, Gly10Ala, Cys2Ala [25]. The *eis* (Cys14Thr) mutation is very specific for resistance to kanamycin than the *eis* (Gly10Cys) and *eis* (Cys12Thr) mutations [43].

The most effective strategy to halt the rise of DR-TB cases is early detection and effective treatment. Rapid molecular tools enable the early detection of DR-TB [44]. Line Probe Assays (LPAs) are molecular diagnostic assays that are used in detecting MTB and its resistance to anti-TB drugs [45]. The Genotype MTBDR_{plus} assay is an LPA that is used for the qualitative identification of MTB and its resistance to RIF and INH, the key first-line anti-TB drugs [46]. While the Genotype MTBDR_{sl} assay is used for the qualitative detection of MTB and its resistance to second-line anti-TB drugs [47]. These assays can use either clinical or cultivated specimens to identify MTB and its resistance [48]. LPAs also

detect gene mutations in MTB that confer resistance to anti-TB drugs [25]. LPAs are recommended by the World Health Organization for diagnosis, guidance on empirical treatment and for surveillance of drug-resistant TB [15]. This study aimed to detect drug-resistant MTB in sputum specimens obtained from the new and previously treated TB cases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and setting

This was a prospective laboratory-based, cross-sectional study that was carried out on TB positive sputum specimens from the new and previously treated TB cases. The study was conducted at the Chest Diseases Laboratory (CDL), in Lusaka, Zambia, from March 2020 to September 2020. CDL is a National Reference TB laboratory that is located at the National Institute for Scientific and Industrial Research (NISIR). CDL has the mandate to perform diagnosis and surveillance for both drug-susceptible and drug-resistant TB. The other key responsibilities for CDL are to conduct trainings in External Quality Assurance (EQA), biosafety, and diagnosis of TB. CDL performs EQA in TB with all provincial laboratories in the country as well as with the Supra-National TB Reference Laboratory in Kampala, Uganda. EQA is performed through blinded rechecking, proficiency testing, and on-site supervision. CDL is accredited by the Southern African Development Community Accreditation Services (SADCAS) of South-Africa.

Specimen processing

Sputum specimens were decontaminated and digested in a class II Biological Safety Cabinet (BSC II) using the N-Acetyl-L-Cysteine-Sodium Hydroxide (NALC-NaOH) method. Briefly, 0.25g of NALC (N-acetyl-L-cysteine) was added in clean falcon tubes, then 50 ml of 4% NaOH (Sodium Hydroxide) and 2.9% $C_6H_5O_7$ (Citrate) mixture was added to the NALC. A physical examination of the sputum specimens was carried out and the volume of each sputum specimen in the falcon tube was recorded. An equal volume of the NALC-NaOH-citrate mixture was added to an equal volume of sputum, then allowed to stand for 15 minutes for digestion and decontamination of the sputum. 1 ml of phosphate buffer solution [pH 6.8] was added to each specimen mixture to neutralize the NaOH, dilute the homogenate and reduce its viscosity and specific gravity. The specimen mixtures were then centrifuged at 3,000 rpm for 20 minutes to concentrate the acid-fast bacilli. After discarding the supernatant into a disinfectant (5% phenol), the sediment was re-suspended in 3 ml phosphate buffer solution and used for fluorescent microscopy and line probe assay. Only confirmed MTB-positive sputum specimens were used for the detection of MTB resistance to the first- and second-line anti-TB drugs.

Detection of drug-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex

DNA extraction from MTB-positive sputum specimens

was done using the GenoLyse kit (Hain Life Science, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Detection of drug-resistance genes in the DNA samples was achieved by two-line probe assays, Genotype MTBDR_{plus} and MTBDR_{sl} assays (Hain Lifescience, Germany), that utilise a Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)-based assay and a hybridization assay performed on an automated GT Blot 48 device (Hain Lifescience, Germany). Both assays were performed strictly according to the manufacturer's instructions. The Genotype MTBDR_{plus} assay was used for detecting resistance against first-line anti-TB drugs, while the MTBDR_{sl} assay was used for detecting resistance to second-line anti-TB drugs.

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using STATA version 13.0 statistical software (StataCorp, Lakeway Drive, College Station, Texas, USA). Pearson's Chi-square test was used to find the association between the different types of drug-resistant TB to age and gender. A *p*-value of less than 0.05 was considered to be statistically significant at 95% confidence interval. Frequencies and percentages were used to determine the level of drug-resistant TB among the new and previously treated TB cases.

Ethics consideration

This was a laboratory-based study, with no direct contact with patients. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Zambia, Ministry of Health, as well the Lusaka Provincial Health Office and the Chest Diseases Laboratory in Lusaka, Zambia. Confidentiality was maintained using study-specific numbers to identify the samples. Integrity, professionalism, and Good Clinical Laboratory Practice (GCLP) standards were maintained throughout the study period. Ethics approval was sought from the University of Zambia, School of Health Sciences, Research and Ethics Committee (UNZA-HSREC) (Ethics Approval Number: 20203101001), while the final clearance and approval to conduct the study was obtained from the National Health Research Authority (NHRA).

RESULTS

Demographic characteristics of the study participants

In this study, a total of 329 sputum specimens were analysed, which translates to 329 cases for drug-resistance TB. The cases were categorized into two groups: the first group comprised 102 (31%) new TB cases, while the second group comprised 227 (69%) previously treated TB cases. Among the new TB cases, 80 (78.4%) were males and 22 (21.6%) females, with an age range of 1-90 years and a median age of 33 (Table 1).

In the previously treated TB cases, there were 166 (73.1%) males and 61 (26.9%) females, with an age range of

Table 1: Distribution of the new and previously treated TB cases by demographic characteristics.

New TB Cases (N = 102)			Previously Treated TB Cases (N = 227)		
Variables	Number (n)	Percentage (%)	Variables	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender			Gender		
Females	22	21.6	Females	60	26.4
Males	80	78.4	Males	167	73.6
Age (years)			Age (years)		
1 - 19	5	4.9	4 - 20	8	3.5
20 - 39	65	63.7	21 - 37	128	56.4
40 - 59	26	25.5	38 - 54	70	30.8
60 - 79	5	4.9	55 - 71	17	7.5
80 - 99	1	1.0	72 - 88	4	1.8

Abbreviations: N: Total Number of Cases; n: Number of Cases; TB: Tuberculosis; Percentage = (n/N) x 100%.

4 -78 years (median age 34 years) (Table 1). The previously treated TB cases comprised treatment failure cases, lost to follow-up cases, relapse cases and defaulter cases. The classification of TB patients into the new and previously treated TB cases is important for surveillance of drug-resistance and treatment. The type of treatment for the new and previously treated TB cases differs, thus a great need for categorization of these cases.

Resistance profiles for first-and second-line anti-TB drugs

The prevalence of the different forms of drug-resistant TB among the new TB cases was as follows: 3.9% had rifampicin mono-resistance, 12.8% isoniazid mono-resistance, and 17.7% had both rifampicin and isoniazid resistance (Table 2). Drug-resistant TB was more prevalent in male cases than female cases, and the age range most affected with drug-resistance was 20-39 years among the new TB cases (Tables 2 & 3).

Table 2: Prevalence of drug-resistance among the new and previously treated TB cases.

Type of drug-resistance	New TB cases (N = 102) No. of cases (n) (%)	Previously treated TB cases (N = 227) No. of cases (n) (%)
Susceptible	67 (65.7%)	108 (47.6%)
Monodrug- resistance		
RIF mono-resistance	4 (3.9%)	23 (10.1%)
INH mono-resistance	13 (12.8%)	15 (6.6%)
Multidrug- resistance		
RIF + INH	18 (17.7%)	75 (33.0%)
Polydrug- resistance		
RIF + FLQs	0 (0%)	4 (1.8%)
Pre-extensively drug resistance		
RIF + INH + FLQs	0 (0%)	1 (0.4%)
RIF + INH + KAN	0 (0%)	1 (0.4%)

Abbreviations: N: Total number of cases; No: Number; RIF: Rifampicin; INH: Isoniazid; FLQs: Fluoroquinolones; KAN: Kanamycin; TB: Tuberculosis; Prevalence = (n/N) x 100%.

Table 3: Association between the different types of drug-resistant TB to demographic variables among the new TB cases.

Demographic variables	Mono-drug-resistance (N = 17)		Multidrug-resistance (N = 18)
	RIF (N = 4) n (%)	INH (N = 13) n (%)	RIF + INH n (%)
Gender			
Females	1 (25%)	2 (15.4%)	2 (11.1%)
Males	3 (75%)	11 (84.6%)	16 (88.9%)
Pearson's Chi-square (X ²)- value	1.4165	2.0583	1.8915
p-value	0.493	0.357	0.388
Age (years)			
1-19	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (5.6%)
20-39	2 (50%)	11 (84.6%)	14 (77.8%)
40-59	1 (25%)	2 (15.4%)	3 (16.7%)
60-79	1 (25%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
80-99	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Pearson's Chi-square (X ²)- value	6.0982	6.9422	5.5664
p-value	0.636	0.543	0.696

Abbreviations: N: Total number of resistant cases; n: Number of resistant cases; RIF: Rifampicin; INH: Isoniazid; TB: Tuberculosis; Percentage = (n/N) X 100%; p < 0.05 statistically significant; p > 0.05 not statistically significant.

The prevalence of the different forms of drug-resistant TB among the previously treated TB cases was as follows: 10.1% had rifampicin mono-resistance, 6.6% isoniazid mono-resistance, 33.0% had both rifampicin and isoniazid resistance, 1.8% had poly-drug resistance, and finally, 0.8% had pre-extensively drug-resistant TB (Tables 2 & 4). The prevalence of drug-resistant TB was more common in males than in females. The age range most affected with drug resistance TB was 21-37 years among the previously treated TB cases (Table 4).

Association between drug-resistant TB types to age and gender among the TB cases

No association was found between the different types

Table 4: Association between the different types of drug-resistant TB to demographic variables among the previously treated TB cases.

Demographic variables	Monodrug-resistance (N = 38)		MDR (N = 75)	Poly-drug resistance (N = 4)	Pre-XDR (N = 1)	Pre-XDR (N = 1)
	RIF (N = 23) n (%)	INH (N = 15) n (%)	RIF + INH n (%)	RIF + FLQs n (%)	RIF + INH + FLQs n (%)	RIF + INH + KAN n (%)
Gender						
Females	6 (26.1%)	5 (33.3%)	23 (30.7%)	1 (25%)	1 (100%)	0 (0%)
Males	17 (73.9%)	10 (66.7%)	52 (69.3%)	3 (75%)	0 (0%)	1 (100%)
Pearson's Chi-square (X ²) value	4.3554	5.0371	1.0331	0.0043	2.7956	0.3609
p-value	0.499	0.284	0.309	0.948	0.095	0.548
Age (years)						
4 - 20	1 (4.3%)	0 (0%)	2 (2.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
21 - 37	18 (78.3%)	9 (60%)	45 (60%)	1 (25%)	1 (100%)	0 (0%)
38 - 54	4 (17.4%)	4 (26.7%)	22 (29.3%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
55 - 71	0 (0%)	2 (13.3%)	6 (8.0%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)	1 (100%)
72 - 88	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Pearson's Chi-square (X ²) value	26.0315	18.5882	2.5878	3.0787	0.7769	12.4076
p-value	0.165	0.291	0.629	0.545	0.942	0.125

Abbreviations: N: Total number of resistant cases; n: number of resistant cases; MDR: Multidrug-Resistance; Pre-XDR: pre-extensively drug resistance; RIF: Rifampicin; INH: Isoniazid; FLQs: Fluoroquinolones; KAN: Kanamycin; Percentage = (n/N) x 100%; p < 0.05 statistically significant; p-value > 0.05 not statistically significant.

of drug-resistant TB to age and gender among the new or previously treated TB cases. All the p-values were above the significant level of 0.05 at 95% confidence interval (Tables 3 and 4).

Frequency of mutations conferring drug-resistance in M. tuberculosis resistant strains

Mutations were detected in the *rpoB*, *katG*, *InhA*, *gyrA*, and *eis* genes of MTB resistant strains. Overall, 34.3% of the cases had mutations detected among the new TB cases and 52.4% among the previously treated TB cases.

Mutations conferring resistance to Rifampicin

From a total of 4 RIF mono-resistant TB cases detected among the new TB cases, the most frequent mutation conferring resistance to RIF was the *rpoB* MUT 3 (Ser531Leu), with a frequency of 75% (Table 5). Among the previously treated TB cases, a total of 23 RIF mono-resistant cases were detected, and the most frequent mutation was the *rpoB* MUT 3 (Ser531Leu), which had a frequency of 56.5% (Table 6).

Mutations conferring resistance to isoniazid

From a total of 13 INH mono-resistant TB cases detected among the new TB cases, the most frequent mutation conferring resistance to INH was the *InhA* MUT 1 (Cys15Thr), with a frequency of 76.9% (Table 5), while a total of 15 INH mono-resistance cases were detected among the previously treated TB cases, with the most frequent mutation being *katG* MUT 1 (Ser315Thr1), 53.3% (Table 6). MTB resistance to INH was detected in the *inhA* and/or *katG* gene(s).

Mutations conferring resistance to both rifampicin and isoniazid

From a total of 18 multi-drug resistance cases detected among the new TB cases, the most frequent mutation conferring resistance to both RIF and INH was a combination of *rpoB* MUT 3 (Ser531Leu) and *katG* MUT 1 (Ser315Thr 1), with a frequency of 27.8% (Table 5). From a total of 75 multi-drug resistant cases detected among the previously treated TB cases, the most frequently detected mutation was a combination of *rpoB* MUT 3 (Ser531Leu) and *katG* MUT 1 (Ser315Thr 1), with a frequency of 29.3% (Table 6).

Mutations conferring resistance to both rifampicin and fluoroquinolones

From a total of 4 poly-drug resistant TB cases detected among the previously treated TB cases, the most frequent mutation conferring resistance to both RIF and fluoroquinolones was a combination of the *rpoB* MUT 2A (His526Tyr) and *gyrA* MUT 1 (Ala90Val), with a frequency of 50% (Table 6).

Mutations conferring resistance to both rifampicin and isoniazid plus fluoroquinolones or kanamycin

Two pre-extensively drug-resistant cases were detected among the previously treated TB cases. One of the cases had a mutation profile of *rpoB* MUT 2B (His526Asp), *katG* MUT 2 (Ser315Thr 2), and *eis* MUT 1 (Cys14Thr). While the other case had a mutation profile of *rpoB* MUT 2A (His526Tyr), *katG* MUT 1 (Ser315Thr), and *gyrA* MUT 3C (Asp94Gly). Each of these profiles had a frequency of 50% (Table 6).

Table 5: Frequency of mutations detected in *M. tuberculosis* resistant isolates among the new TB cases.

Genes implicated in drug-resistance	Genotypic profile of drug-resistance	Mutations detected	No. of MTB isolates	Frequency (%)
	Mono drug resistance (n = 17)			
rpoB	Rifampicin (n = 4)			
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 1	Asp516Val	1	1/4 (25%)
	rpoB MUT 3/Δ rpoB WT 8	Ser531Leu	3	3/4 (75%)
InhA or katG	Isoniazid (n = 13)			
	InhA MUT 1/Δ InhA WT 1	Cys15Thr	10	10/13 (76.9%)
	<i>katG</i> MUT 1	Ser315Thr 1	3	3/13 (23.1%)
	Multidrug-resistance (n = 18)			
rpoB + katG or InhA	Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 8 Δ <i>katG</i> WT	Ser531Leu C-315	1	1/18 (5.6%)
	rpoB MUT 3/Δ rpoB WT 8 katG MUT 1/Δ katG WT	Ser531Leu Ser315Thr 1	5	5/18 (27.8%)
	Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 2 <i>InhA</i> MUT 1	Glu510His Cys15Thr	1	1/18 (5.6%)
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 3 <i>InhA</i> MUT 1	Ser531Leu Cys15Thr	1	1/18 (5.6%)
	Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 2 <i>InhA</i> MUT 1/Δ <i>InhA</i> WT 1	Glu510His Cys15Thr	1	1/18 (5.6%)
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 2B/Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 7 <i>katG</i> MUT 1/Δ <i>katG</i> WT	His526Asp Ser315Thr 1	1	1/18 (5.6%)
	Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 3/Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 4 <i>katG</i> MUT 1/Δ <i>katG</i> WT	Asp516Val Ser315Thr 1	2	2/18 (11.1%)
	Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 1 Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 2 Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 8 <i>InhA</i> MUT 1/Δ <i>InhA</i> WT 1	C 505-509 Glu510His Ser531Leu Cys15Thr	1	1/18 (5.6%)
	Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 8 <i>katG</i> MUT 2	Ser531Leu Ser315Thr 2	1	1/18 (5.6%)
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 2B <i>rpoB</i> MUT 3 <i>katG</i> MUT 1	His526Asp Ser531Leu Ser315Thr 1	1	1/18 (5.6%)
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 2B <i>katG</i> MUT 1	His526Asp Ser315Thr 1	1	1/18 (5.6%)
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 2A /Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 7 <i>katG</i> MUT 1/Δ <i>katG</i> WT	His526Tyr Ser315Thr 1	1	1/18 (5.6%)
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 3/Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 8 <i>InhA</i> MUT 1/Δ <i>InhA</i> WT 1	Ser531Leu Cys15Thr	1	1/18 (5.6%)

Abbreviations: Δ: deletion; WT: Wild Type; MUT: Mutation; ΔWT/MUT: deletion of the wild-type probe and presence of mutation; C: Codon; TB: Tuberculosis; MTB: *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*; Ala: Alanine; Asp: Aspartic acid; Cys: Cysteine; Glu: Glutamic acid; Gly: Glycine; His: Histidine; Leu: Leucine; Ser: Serine; Thr: Threonine; Tyr: Tyrosine; Val: Valine. Mutations with the highest frequency are bold in black.

DISCUSSION

This study highlights the growing threat posed by the emergence of resistant MTB strains responsible for causing the different types of drug-resistant TB in Zambia. The majority of patients identified with drug-resistant TB had a history of being treated for TB previously and interrupted first-line anti-TB therapy. These factors are predictors of the emergence of drug-resistant TB [49-51]. In this study, drug-resistant-TB was found to be high among the previously treated TB patients than among the new TB patients. Drug-resistant TB was high among adult males than females, because of social stigma, cultural habits and poor health-seeking behaviour among males [52].

The prevalence of Rifampicin Resistant (RR)-TB in

our study was 3.9% among the new TB cases and 10.1% among the previously treated TB cases. These findings are consistent with the findings reported elsewhere. A previous study conducted in Zambia reported a prevalence for RR at 5.9% among the previously treated TB cases [20]. A similar study conducted in Zimbabwe found the prevalence of RR to be 4.0% among the new TB cases and 14.2% among the previously treated TB cases [53], while a South-African found the burden of RR to be 8.8% among the previously treated TB cases [54]. In Burkina Faso, the prevalence of RR was found at 2.0% and 14.5% among the new and previously treated TB cases, respectively [55]. RR-TB is associated with a history of being treated for TB previously. Therefore, improvement in adherence to treatment halts the emergence or re-emergence of MTB and RR-TB cases [56]. The differences in the reported prevalence for RR-TB from other countries can

Table 6: Frequency of mutations detected in *M. tuberculosis* resistant isolates among the previously treated TB cases.

Genes implicated in drug-resistance	Genotypic profile of drug-resistance	Mutations detected	No. of MTB isolates	Frequency (%)	
rpoB	Mono drug resistance (n = 38)				
	Rifampicin (n = 23)				
	rpoB MUT 3/Δ rpoB WT 8	Ser531Leu	13	13/23 (56.5%)	
InhA and/or katG	Isoniazid (n = 15)				
	<i>InhA</i> MUT 1/Δ <i>InhA</i> WT 1	Cys15Thr	5	5/15 (33.3%)	
	katG MUT 1/Δ katG WT	Ser315Thr 1	8	8/15 (53.3%)	
	<i>katG</i> MUT1 <i>InhA</i> MUT 1/Δ <i>InhA</i> WT 1	Ser315Thr 1 Cys15Thr	1	1/15(6.7%)	
rpoB + katG &/or InhA	Multidrug-resistance (n = 75)				
	rpoB MUT 3/Δ rpoB WT 8 katG MUT 1/Δ katG WT	Ser531Leu Ser315Thr 1	22	22/75 (29.3%)	
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 2B/Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 7 <i>katG</i> MUT1/Δ <i>katG</i> WT	His526Asp Ser315Thr 1	20	20/75 (26.7%)	
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 1 <i>katG</i> MUT1/Δ <i>katG</i> WT	Asp516Val Ser315Thr 1	1	1/75 (1.3%)	
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 2B <i>rpoB</i> MUT 3 <i>katG</i> MUT1 <i>InhA</i> MUT 1	His526Asp Ser531Leu Ser315Thr 1 Cys15Thr	1	1/75 (1.3%)	
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 2A <i>katG</i> MUT1/Δ <i>katG</i> WT	His526Tyr Ser315Thr 1	1	1/75 (1.3%)	
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 1 Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 3/Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 4 <i>katG</i> MUT 2/Δ <i>katG</i> WT	Asp516Val Ser315Thr 2	1	1/75 (1.3%)	
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 3/Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 8 <i>InhA</i> MUT 1/Δ <i>InhA</i> WT 1	Ser531Leu Cys15Thr	2	2/75 (2.7%)	
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 2B <i>InhA</i> MUT 1	His526Asp Cys15Thr	1	1/75 (1.3%)	
	rpoB + gyrA	Poly drug- resistance (n = 4)			
		<i>rpoB</i> MUT 2 A Δ <i>gyrA</i> WT 2 Δ <i>gyrA</i> WT 3	His526Tyr C 89-93 C 92-96	1	1/4 (25)
rpoB MUT 2 A/Δ rpoB WT 7 gyrA MUT 1/Δ gyrA WT 2		His526Tyr Ala90Val	2	2/4 (50%)	
<i>rpoB</i> MUT 2 A/Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 7 Δ <i>gyrA</i> WT 2		His526Tyr C 89-93	1	1/4 (25)	
rpoB + katG + gyrA	Pre- extensively drug-resistance (n=2)				
	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 2A/Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 7 <i>katG</i> MUT 1 /Δ <i>katG</i> WT <i>gyrA</i> MUT 3C/Δ <i>gyrA</i> WT 3	His526Tyr Ser315Thr 1 Asp94Gly	1	1/2 (50%)	
rpoB + katG + eis	<i>rpoB</i> MUT 2B/Δ <i>rpoB</i> WT 7 <i>katG</i> MUT 2/Δ <i>katG</i> WT <i>eis</i> MUT 1	His526Asp Ser315Thr 2 Cys14Thr	1	1/2 (50%)	

Abbreviations: Δ deletion; WT: Wild Type; MUT: Mutation; ΔWT/MUT: deletion of the wild-type probe and presence of mutation; C: Codon; TB: Tuberculosis; MTB: *Mycobacterium Tuberculosis*; Ala: Alanine; Asp: Aspartic acid; Cys: Cysteine; Glu: Glutamic acid; Gly: Glycine; His: Histidine; Leu: Leucine; Ser: Serine; Thr: Threonine; Tyr: Tyrosine; Val: Valine. Mutations with the highest frequency are bold in black.

be attributed to differences in the sample size used, study settings, study design, the method employed, differences in socio-economic factors, differences in case management of drug-resistant TB, and many other factors.

The prevalence of Isoniazid Mono-Resistance (INHr)-TB in our study was 12.8% and 6.6% among the new and previously treated TB cases, respectively. These findings are consistent with other regions of the world. A low prevalence of INHr among the new TB cases was reported in Tanzania (7.6%) [57], and Ethiopia (9.5%) [58]. Similar studies in South-Korea and Pakistan reported 11% and 9.8%,

respectively, for INHr-TB among new TB cases [59,60]. INHr is more common than RR and is a growing public health problem globally because research and policy directions are only focused on RR as a marker for MDR-TB. However, this growing problem of INHr is being ignored globally [61].

MDR-TB is one of the most serious public health problems in the world [55,62]. Its prevalence is increasing in every part of the world today, for both new and previously treated TB cases [63]. In the current study, the prevalence of MDR-TB was high, 17.7% among the new TB cases and 33.0% among the previously treated TB cases. These

findings were consistent with those reported in India in which the prevalence of MDR-TB was found to be 11.4% and 36.4% among the new and the previously treated TB cases, respectively [64]. Another study conducted in Ethiopia reported 11.6% and 32.7% MDR prevalence among the new and previously treated cases, respectively [65], while that in China reported the prevalence of MDR-TB at 30.4% among the previously treated cases [66]. MDR-TB is a growing public health threat in Zambia, and the WHO has projected that by 2021 the country will have a high burden of the disease [23,24]. DR-TB is not caused by a single factor, but by several factors which come into play and some of these include: poor adherence to TB treatment, irregular supply and stock-out of anti-TB drugs, inappropriate TB therapy, delayed diagnosis and initiation of ineffective therapy as well as spontaneous chromosomal mutations [1,30,33,58]. Liang and colleagues in their study found that inappropriate treatment was the most common cause of MDR-TB [66]. Failure to implement effective TB prevention and control measures also facilitates the emergence of the different forms of DR-TB including MDR-TB [67-69]. The key factors above including treatment failure, TB relapse, treatment defaulting, MDR contacts, loss to follow-up cases, and misdiagnosis could be contributing to the reasons for the observed rise in the number of MDR-TB cases in Zambia. MDR-TB must be managed effectively to reduce mortality, morbidity, and the eventual transmission of MTB resistant strains [70].

In this study, the prevalence of poly drug-resistant TB was found to be low (1.8%) among the previously treated TB cases. This finding was similar to studies conducted in Ethiopia (2.3%) and Canada (0.4%) [71,72]. However, studies elsewhere reported a high prevalence of poly drug-resistance among the previously treated: India reported 12.0% prevalence [64], Bangladesh 8.6% [72] and Sudan 6.4% [72]. Poor case management of mono-drug resistant TB results in poly drug-resistant TB.

The prevalence of pre-XDR TB in our study was low (0.8%) among the previously treated TB cases. This result is similar to that reported in Ethiopia, 5.7% [73]. Studies elsewhere reported a high prevalence of pre-XDR: India (56%), China (34%), Nepal (28%), Zimbabwe (27%), Nigeria (17%) and Bangladesh (16.2%) [73-75]. The high prevalence of pre-XDR TB can indicate poor management of MDR-TB cases. Poorly managed MDR-TB cases progress to pre-XDR TB, which eventually get to XDR-TB.

In this study, no association was found between the different types of Drug-Resistance (DR) to age and gender among the new and previously treated TB cases. This finding was similar to other countries such as Sudan [76], Nigeria [77], Ethiopia [78], and Egypt [79]. Age and gender were not associated with drug-resistance because these variables are not significant risk factors. Studies have shown that the key risk factors associated with the development of drug-

resistant TB include: history of previous treatment for TB, poor adherence to TB treatment, inadequate supply and stock-out of anti-TB drugs, poor management of TB, and contact with DR-TB patients [30,33,58,78-79].

Drug-resistant MTB strains use various complex mechanisms to inactivate or resist anti-TB drugs. Among these are point mutations in chromosomal genes, which can be an insertion, deletion or missense [80-82]. Molecular assays detect mutations that confer resistance to anti-TB drugs. In this study the *rpoB* MUT 3 (Ser531Leu) mutation was the most frequently detected (75%), conferring resistance to rifampicin, among the new TB cases. This result is similar to that reported in Brazil (75%) [83], and in Ethiopia (74.2% and 77.1%) [84,85]. In contrast, other studies elsewhere reported a low frequency of the mutation, with Canada reporting 47.8% [86], India reporting 46.9% and 19.5% in two separate studies [82,87], and Uganda reporting 40% [37]. Based on these results it suffices to say, mutation frequencies vary from one geographical location to another due to differences in the epidemiology of TB, differences in geographic transmission environments for MTB, as well as differences in treatment combinations used in the management of cases.

The *katG* MUT 1 (Ser315Thr 1) mutation was the most frequently (53.3%) encountered mutation conferring resistance to INH among the previously treated TB cases in this current study. This finding is consistent with studies in Taiwan (50.4%), Myanmar (57.3%) and India (57.8%) [1,88]. Studies have shown that 50-95% of MTB resistant strains have mutations in the *katG* gene [44]. A high frequency of the *katG* Ser315Thr 1 mutation is associated with countries with a high prevalence of TB, such as Zambia [44]. The *InhA* MUT1 (Cys15Thr) mutation was also frequently (76.9%) detected among the new TB cases in this current study and this finding is consistent with findings from similar studies in other countries such as Ethiopia (77.5%) [85], South-Africa (70.1%) [89], and India (85.9%) [1]. It has been shown that the Ser315Thr 1 mutation is the most frequent in the *katG* gene that confers resistance to INH, while the Cys15Thr mutation is the most frequent in the *InhA* gene that confer resistance to INH [90].

Mutations conferring resistance to both RIF and INH were detected in our study. These mutations are responsible for causing MDR-TB. The *rpoB* MUT 3 (Ser531Leu) and the *katG* MUT1 (Ser315Thr 1) mutations were the most frequent (27.8%) conferring resistance to both RIF and INH, among the new TB cases. This same mutation was the most frequent among the previously treated TB cases. These findings are similar to results obtained in Thailand (36.4%) [25].

This study also detected other mutations such as the *rpoB* MUT 2A (His526Tyr) and *gyrA* MUT 1 (Ala90Val) with a frequency of 50%, that confer resistance to both RIF and FLQs among the previously treated TB cases and was consistent

with findings reported in Ethiopia where the mutational frequency was found to be 50% [65]. The Ala90Val mutation is associated with high-level resistance to FLQs [41]. Studies have shown that most mutations associated with FLQ resistance occur in the *gyrA* gene on codon 90–94 of MTB resistant strains [65]. This is in agreement with our findings. Misuse of FLQ antibiotics has contributed to resistance in MTB strains, associated with mutations in the *gyrA* gene [41,42].

In this study other multiple mutations detected were associated with resistance in the *rpoB*, *katG*, *gyrA* and *eis* genes. These combined mutation profiles were responsible for causing pre-XDR TB and each had a frequency of 50%. One of these combination mutations had a profile: *rpoB* MUT 2B (His526Asp), *katG* MUT 2 (Ser315Thr 2), and *eis* MUT 1 (Cys14Thr). The other had *rpoB* MUT 2A (His526Tyr), *katG* MUT 1 (Ser315Thr), and *gyrA* MUT 3C (Asp94Gly). Unlike the high frequency of these mutations in this study, studies elsewhere, such as Morocco and India, reported low mutational frequency in these genes [3,91]. Mismanagement of DR-TB cases result in resistance associated with multiple mutations in MTB genes.

CONCLUSION

Drug-resistant TB is prevalent in Zambia, especially MDR-TB, is hampering efforts in the control of TB. DR-TB is mainly caused by mutations in the target genes of resistant MTB strains. Mutations identified in this study were the *rpoB* (Ser531Leu, His526Asp, Asp516Val, His526Tyr, and Glu510His), *InhA* (Cys15Thr), *gyrA* (Ala90Val and Asp94Gly), *katG* (Ser315Thr 1 and Ser315Thr 2), and *eis* (Cys14Thr), each with a varying frequency. Zambia needs to scale-up on the number of laboratory sites performing genotypic drug-susceptibility testing, effectively treat DR-TB, especially MDR-TB, and implement effective TB control strategies to combat DR-TB.

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